

From Pilot to Practice: Business Model Innovation for 5G-Enabled Bidirectional Charging in Smart Cities

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Abstract: This paper presents a **barrier-detection business model framework** for 5G-enabled bidirectional electric vehicle (EV) charging, grounded in technical pilots and simulation studies in Dresden’s Ostra district. Using real-world operational data and direct stakeholder engagement, we identify the practical value propositions, cost structures, and incentive mechanisms necessary for scalable Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) and Vehicle-to-Building (V2B) adoption in urban settings. The analysis systematically maps socio-technical and regulatory barriers, including market, infrastructure, and user acceptance challenges, and proposes actionable, stakeholder-driven pathways for smart city integration. Our findings show that advanced communication networks, combined with collaborative business models, can accelerate the transition to sustainable urban mobility and resilient energy systems. The work delivers a transferable framework for evaluating V2G/V2B integration, supporting both local policy development and broader academic discourse on digital energy transitions.

1 INTRODUCTION

Urban centers lead the global sustainability transition, decarbonizing transport via the European Green Deal [Rimpas et al., 2025]. Electric vehicles (EVs) offer emissions reductions and better air quality [Hsieh et al., 2022], but widespread adoption strains grids with peak demand, congestion, and storage needs [Micari and Napoli, 2024]. Bidirectional charging and Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) transform EVs into distributed energy resources, enabling grid stability, renewable integration, and economic opportunities for owners and utilities [Wang et al., 2024a, Zhou et al., 2021, Noel et al., 2018]. Yet despite technical readiness, deployment stalls due to regulatory, market, and user barriers [Hu et al., 2025, Willemse, 2019].

Our Dresden research program addresses these challenges in three phases. First, traffic and charging simulations for the Ostra district demonstrated the potential of coordinated charging and V2G to reduce peak loads and improve renewable utilization [Wang et al., 2025a]. Second, a real-world communication

interface was implemented between driver applications, EVs, charging infrastructure, and a control optimizer, closing the loop between user inputs, state-of-charge information, and charging control in an intelligent bidirectional charging setup [Wang et al., 2025b]. Building on these technical foundations, the present work represents the third phase, focusing on how business models and institutional arrangements can either enable or block the scaling of such pilots in real urban contexts.

5G enables real-time V2G via low latency and high reliability [Wang et al., 2024b]. The planned Ostra pilot integrates two 50 kW charging stations and three EVs via a private communication platform [MobilitiesforEU, 2024], creating a testbed for business model design and future validation. However, experience from previous pilots shows that technical feasibility alone is insufficient [Wang et al., 2024a]. Robust business models must align EV owners, utilities, cities, and service providers amid regulatory and market challenges [Santos et al., 2025, Zhou et al., 2021]. V2G co-benefits (resilience, community value) also require clear communication to overcome Dresden

stakeholders’ “*faraway water*” gap problem—future potential versus present needs [Noel et al., 2018].

The objective of this paper is to develop and demonstrate a practical business model framework for 5G-enabled bidirectional electric vehicle charging in urban environments, using the Dresden Ostra district as a case study. We systematically integrate simulation results, pilot design, and stakeholder analysis to identify value propositions, estimate costs and benefits, and surface key regulatory and market barriers. Rather than proposing a purely profit-maximizing scheme, the business model is used as a **barrier detection tool** to systematically reveal blockers to scaling. By doing so, we aim to provide actionable strategies and policy recommendations that support the scalable adoption of V2G/V2B solutions in smart cities and contribute to the broader transition toward sustainable urban mobility and resilient energy systems.

2 Related Work: Positioning

Bidirectional charging, enabling two-way energy flows between EVs and the grid or home, has emerged as a key innovation for advancing grid flexibility, resilience, and the integration of renewable energy sources. Technologies such as V2G/V2B allow EVs to act as distributed energy storage, supporting peak shaving, backup power, and dynamic load management [Adegbohun et al., 2024]. While the technical feasibility of bidirectional charging is established, large-scale adoption remains limited by interoperability challenges, regulatory uncertainty, and the need for robust business models [Adegbohun et al., 2024, Zhou et al., 2021, Onkalo, 2024].

Recent literature reviews and market reports highlight that most commercial bidirectional charging solutions currently rely on direct current infrastructure, which can be costly and requires compatible vehicles [Zhou et al., 2021, Habib et al., 2018]. The market for bidirectional chargers is expected to grow rapidly, with new products and regulatory changes pushing the technology closer to mainstream adoption, especially as more automakers and energy companies invest in compatible hardware and software platforms [Wouters and Martinez, 2023, Habib et al., 2018]. However, both technology and standards development must be accompanied by viable business cases that balance costs, benefits, and stakeholder incentives across the value chain [Onkalo, 2024, Zhou et al., 2021].

Business model research emphasizes the importance of aligning the interests of EV owners, utilities,

fleet operators, and technology providers [Onkalo, 2024, Santos et al., 2025, Zhou et al., 2021]. For individual users, bidirectional charging can offer operational savings and backup power, but incentives or revenue streams—such as participation in grid services or virtual power plants—are needed to drive adoption [Zhou et al., 2021]. For commercial fleets, predictable duty cycles and large battery capacities present unique opportunities for monetizing grid services and improving return on investment [Santos et al., 2025, Zhou et al., 2021]. Nevertheless, customer acceptance, battery degradation concerns, and regulatory fragmentation remain significant barriers [Santos et al., 2025, Rimpas et al., 2025].

Complementing these findings, our prior work demonstrated bidirectional charging impacts in Dresden’s Ostra district. We developed a simulation architecture [Wang et al., 2025a] and explored 5G’s role in real-time coordination [Wang et al., 2024b, Wang et al., 2024a, MobilitiesforEU, 2024]. These studies underscore the importance of integrating digital infrastructure, stakeholder engagement, and policy frameworks to bridge the gap between technical readiness and market adoption.

In summary, while the technical and economic potential of bidirectional charging is well recognized, the literature consistently highlights the need for holistic business models, supportive regulation, and digital platforms to unlock scalable, user-centric solutions for smart cities. Building on these insights and on the planned Dresden Ostra pilot, this paper employs a Business Model Canvas (BMC) framework as a **barrier detection tool** for 5G-enabled bidirectional charging in urban environments.

3 Methodology: Business Model Canvas as Barrier Detector

Our methodology moves beyond technical optimization to address barriers that prevent university innovations from achieving real-world impact. We combine the planned Ostra pilot design, simulation insights [Wang et al., 2025a], and stakeholder mapping to derive 5G-enabled bidirectional charging business models.

3.1 Pilot Data and Simulation Integration:

At the core of our approach is the Dresden Ostra district pilot, which is currently in the implementation phase and will integrate two 50 kW bidirectional

charging stations and three EVs via a private 5G platform. At this stage, the business model and barrier analysis are informed by the planned technical design, by simulation results, and by stakeholder workshops, rather than by long-term operational logs. To assess scalability and transferability, we rely on simulation models built on a traffic simulation platform and custom energy management algorithms for Ostra [Wang et al., 2025a], which allow us to anticipate infrastructure requirements, grid impacts, and user behaviour at scale.

3.2 Stakeholder Mapping and Ecosystem Analysis:

Recognizing that the primary barriers to technology transfer are often socio-technical rather than purely technical, we conducted a structured stakeholder mapping exercise, shown in Table 1. Stakeholders were identified and analyzed through interviews, project workshops, and a review of local policy documents. Key groups include EV owners, utilities, city authorities, fleet operators, and technology providers. For each group, we systematically mapped roles, incentives, and pain points, with a particular focus on regulatory, infrastructure, and market readiness challenges. This process revealed not only technical limitations but also regulatory ambiguities, fragmented responsibilities, and misaligned incentives that can stall or derail implementation efforts. The stakeholder roles and goals summarized in Table 1 are based on project documentation, semi-structured interviews, and consortium workshops with representatives of each group. While these roles have been discussed and refined with stakeholders, their practical validity will be further tested once the Ostra pilot is fully operational.

3.3 Business Model Analysis Framework:

The Business Model Canvas (BMC) was developed by the research team using simulation insights, stakeholder mapping, and experience from previous V2G projects. It has been reviewed in internal project workshops, but remains a design-stage artefact that will be empirically evaluated and adjusted during the upcoming Ostra pilot operation. Following best practices for EV charging business models [Weiller and Neely, 2013, MOSELE and NERI, 2019], we use the BMC not only to outline commercial elements but also to systematically identify and address the technical, regulatory, and market barriers that arise during implementation. Each component—value propo-

sition, customer segments, channels, partnerships, revenue streams, and cost structure—was iteratively refined using simulation results and ongoing stakeholder engagement.

In our BMC, the **value proposition** focuses on grid flexibility, user incentives, CO₂ reduction, and resilience for **customer segments** including private EV owners, commercial fleets, and city infrastructure. **Channels** and **customer relationships** are based on mobile apps, fleet management platforms, public-private partnerships, automated digital engagement, loyalty schemes, and community incentives. **Revenue streams** (energy sales, grid services, subscription and data-driven services) are supported by **key resources** such as 5G network infrastructure, OCPP-compliant charging stations, and data analytics, as well as **key activities** like real-time energy management, user engagement, and maintenance. **Key partnerships** with utilities, city government, technology vendors, and fleet operators operate under a **cost structure** covering hardware and installation, software/IT, maintenance, and customer acquisition.

3.4 Integrating Barriers and Enablers into the Model

Throughout the methodology, particular attention was paid to identifying and categorizing the barriers and enablers encountered. These were grouped into regulatory, market, infrastructure, and user acceptance domains. For each barrier, we explored potential enablers—such as regulatory sandboxes, tariff reforms, or public-private partnerships—and evaluated how these could be operationalized within the business model. This structured approach ensures that both technical and business perspectives are addressed and that the resulting model is adaptable to evolving market and policy conditions [Afentoulis et al., 2022].

4 Results: A Business Model for 5G-Enabled Bidirectional Charging

This work provides a transferable framework for evaluating and accelerating V2G/V2B integration, based on systematic identification of barriers and stakeholder-driven solutions. Our results synthesize technical, market, and stakeholder insights into a business model that is innovative yet grounded in the practical realities of technology transfer.

Table 1: Stakeholder Groups, Pilot Contributions, and Long-Term Goals

Stakeholder Group	Pilot Contribution	Long-Term Goal
University Research Partner	Integration of advanced V2B/V2G technology and data analysis	Academic publications and intellectual property development
City Government	Facilitation of EV integration at municipal facilities and permitting for infrastructure	Scalable blueprint for city-wide V2G deployment
Data Platform Provider	Integration of mobility and energy data platforms	Commercial smart mobility service offerings
Regional Utility	Testing real-time grid response with V2G-enabled assets	Co-development of revenue-neutral grid service tariffs
Facility Operator	Hosting charging infrastructure and providing real-world usage data	Enhanced facility energy resilience and optimized charging incentives
Charging Hardware Provider	Installation and maintenance of bidirectional charging stations	Long-term service contracts and hardware standardization
Automotive Manufacturer	No direct pilot role; potential for technical validation	Future validation and adoption of V2X protocols

4.1 Value Creation

The proposed business model creates distinct value for multiple stakeholder groups. For **EV owners**, it offers the potential to earn additional income from grid services, reduce charging costs via dynamic pricing, and access backup power during outages. For **utilities**, it provides flexible, distributed storage for peak shaving and frequency regulation, reducing reliance on costly stationary batteries. For **the city**, district-scale simulations for Ostra show up to 18% peak-load reduction [Wang et al., 2025a], which improves grid resilience, facilitates CO₂ mitigation, and aligns with smart city sustainability goals. The primary value at this stage is therefore not direct financial return, but the systematic identification and resolution of barriers to V2G/V2B adoption and the provision of a transferable integration framework.

4.2 Cost Structure and Revenue Streams:

Capital Expenditure (CAPEX). Design-stage CAPEX estimates for the planned Ostra deployment are:

- Bidirectional charging stations: 2 units at €8,000 each (\approx €16,000)
- Installation and commissioning: €2,000
- Software/app development, system integration, and building upgrades: €25,000
- Project management and technical coordination: €10,000
- Workshops and regulatory dialogue: €5,000

The 5G connectivity infrastructure is financed under a separate action, leading to a total CAPEX of ap-

proximately €58,000. These figures combine project budget allocations with supplier quotations and are intended as realistic order-of-magnitude estimates for a small-scale demonstrator.

Operational Expenditure (OPEX, per year). Projected annual OPEX includes:

- Maintenance of charging infrastructure: €1,000
- Software and platform support: €2,000
- Connectivity service fees: €1,000
- Energy costs: €5,500 (27,500 kWh at €0.20/kWh)

This results in a total projected OPEX of about €9,500 per year. Actual values will be refined once the pilot is in operation.

Revenue streams and business viability. At the planned scale of two chargers and three EVs, direct revenue from grid services, energy arbitrage, or subscriptions is negligible. The primary “return” of this initial deployment is expected to be knowledge generation, identification of regulatory, market, user, and infrastructure barriers, and the development of a transferable framework for future business models and policy. In larger, mature deployments, potential revenue streams could include grid services (e.g., frequency regulation, peak shaving), energy arbitrage, and data-driven services [BusinessConceptor, 2025, Pod, 2025]. A simple extrapolation of the above CAPEX and OPEX figures indicates that, under current German tariff and taxation conditions, the planned pilot size is far below the scale at which V2G/V2B revenues could cover marginal operating costs. Business viability, therefore, requires both aggregation to larger fleets and regulatory reforms (such as reduced double taxation and more attractive flexibility tariffs), which our barrier-detection framework

makes visible but does not itself resolve. In this sense, the Ostra pilot is intentionally positioned as a knowledge-generation and “blocker removal” step prior to any fully commercial rollout.

4.3 Discussion: Lessons Learned, 5G Role, and Scalability

Experience from our previous 5G experiments for V2G control [Wang et al., 2024b] and from the planned Ostra deployment indicates that the 5G communication layer is essential for robust real-time coordination between EVs, buildings, and the control optimizer, supporting seamless integration of bidirectional charging into grid and building operations [Zaidan et al., 2022]. Addressing regulatory, market, infrastructure, and user barriers requires a systems approach, combining tariff reforms, regulatory sandboxes, and incentive mechanisms within the business model to enhance both technical and economic viability [Zaidan et al., 2022]. While immediate business value remains limited at pilot scale, simulation results suggest that wider deployment could deliver substantial grid flexibility and sustainability benefits. The developed business model and evaluation framework are transferable, offering a practical template for other cities aiming to accelerate bidirectional charging adoption [Wang et al., 2025a].

5 Barriers and Enablers: Socio-Technical and Policy Insights

Building on the cost and revenue analysis above, Table 2 summarizes the socio-technical barriers identified for the Dresden case, grouped into four categories: regulatory, market, user acceptance, and infrastructure. We analyze how these barriers affect scaling and highlight incentives and business model solutions, providing actionable insights for urban V2G deployment. We focus on these four domains because they consistently emerged in stakeholder interviews, project workshops, and previous V2G/V2X gap analyses. Earlier studies often address these dimensions separately (e.g., concentrating only on regulation or only on user behaviour); by embedding them into a single BMC-based framework, we explicitly link each barrier category to concrete business model building blocks and responsible stakeholders.

5.1 Regulatory Barriers

Our pilot underscores that the absence of a harmonized legal framework for bidirectional charging remains the primary obstacle to widespread adoption in Germany and across Europe [Tezel et al., 2019, go e, 2024, Zahler et al., 2025, Thomas et al., 2023]. Uncertainties persist around metering, grid connection, and data access, compounded by double taxation and grid fees on electricity fed back to the grid, which erode the economic case for V2G participation [Zinglarsen, 2023, go e, 2024, Thomas et al., 2023, Zahler et al., 2025, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024]. Outdated or insufficient technical standards further hinder interoperability and safety, slowing the transition from pilot projects to scalable solutions [Zahler et al., 2025, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024]. National and EU-level policy efforts are underway to address these issues, but as of 2025, practical implementation lags behind technical readiness [Thomas et al., 2023, Zahler et al., 2025, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024].

5.2 Market Barriers

High grid connection costs and the lack of targeted financial incentives continue to deter investment in bidirectional charging, especially for small-scale or demonstration projects like ours [National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, Thomas et al., 2023]. The absence of well-defined revenue streams and aggregation mechanisms limits market participation, while fragmented stakeholder responsibilities and low EV adoption further reduce economies of scale [National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, Thomas et al., 2023]. Additionally, insufficient data-sharing frameworks complicate integration with energy markets and grid operators [Power2Drive, 2025].

5.3 User Acceptance Barriers

User acceptance presents another set of challenges. Many potential users remain unaware of the benefits and business models associated with bidirectional charging, and concerns about battery degradation, warranty coverage, and participation complexity persist [Thomas et al., 2023, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024]. The lack of clear, consistent financial incentives and real-world success stories further weakens the value proposition for end-users [Thomas et al., 2023, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH),

Table 2: Summary of Key Barriers and Enablers for V2G/V2B Adoption

Barrier Category	Examples	Proposed Enablers
Regulatory	Double taxation on V2G/V2B energy, inconsistent grid connection rules, lack of harmonized standards	Policy advocacy, regulatory sandboxes, harmonization of standards, pilot-friendly legislation
Market	High upfront charger costs, limited revenue streams, uncertain business models	Public-private partnerships, targeted incentives, aggregator models, flexible tariff design
User acceptance	Battery degradation concerns, low user awareness, data privacy concerns	User education, clear warranty terms, transparent data policies, demonstration projects
Infrastructure	Lack of plug-and-play standards, legacy grid limitations, insufficient data exchange	Open standards, vendor collaboration, infrastructure upgrades, digitalization initiatives

Note: Adoption [Thomas et al., 2023, Afrasiabi et al., 2023, Simolin et al., 2024]. The literature-derived barriers in this table were cross-checked against Ostra evidence: double taxation and grid connection uncertainty were raised by the regional utility and city officials as obstacles to scaling from two chargers to a larger mobility hub, while low user awareness and battery degradation concerns surfaced in discussions with the facility operator and early EV users, confirming that these barriers are locally actionable.

2024, pv Europe, 2025].

5.4 Infrastructure Barriers

Bidirectional charging infrastructure faces significant technical and economic challenges [National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, Thomas et al., 2023, Power2Drive, 2025]. High upfront costs, complex retrofitting in existing urban environments, and the need for grid upgrades are major obstacles [National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, Thomas et al., 2023]. Integration with legacy building and distribution systems often requires customized solutions due to limited standardization and interoperability of hardware and software [Power2Drive, 2025, go e, 2024]. Moreover, the lack of robust, high-bandwidth connectivity limits real-time control capabilities, although emerging 5G deployments are beginning to mitigate this issue [Zahler et al., 2025, Thomas et al., 2023]. These challenges are exacerbated in areas with low EV penetration, where limited demand weakens the investment case and leads to fragmented deployments [National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, Thomas et al., 2023].

Applying the BMC as a barrier-detection tool to the Ostra case yields several specific insights. First, key partnerships and revenue streams emerge as the weakest blocks: utilities and city planners provide essential infrastructure and regulatory support, yet were not directly involved in designing concrete user incentives or tariffs in the current pilot. Second, user-facing value propositions such as backup power and dynamic tariffs are not yet matched by dedicated channels or relationship models, which helps explain the ‘faraway water’ perception among local stakeholders. Third, mapping barriers to individual BMC blocks reveals

where targeted policy instruments—such as regulatory sandboxes for grid connection rules or public procurement for bidirectional chargers—would have the highest leverage. These are new learnings that only become visible when technical pilots are systematically translated into business model components.

6 Addressing Barriers: Incentives and Business Model Innovations

6.1 Identified Need: Incentive Mechanisms

While user-facing apps and digital platforms can technically enable real-time feedback and flexible participation in grid services, our case highlights that robust incentive mechanisms—such as participation rewards, dynamic tariffs, and streamlined interconnection—are not yet in place. Utilities and city partners have not been directly involved in designing these incentives, underscoring a key gap for future pilots. We recommend that future deployments prioritize collaborative development of user and stakeholder incentives, with active engagement from utilities and city planners, to align interests and accelerate market adoption.

6.2 Business Model Response and Remaining Gaps

Our business model is designed not as a profit engine, but as a framework for systematically identifying and addressing barriers to V2G/V2B adoption. By proposing revenue-sharing schemes, dynamic tariffs, and open standards, it aims to make participation

more attractive and future-proof for all stakeholders. Strategic partnerships with grid operators and technology providers are essential for coordinated integration, while user engagement and transparent communication are prioritized to build trust and acceptance.

Despite these efforts, significant gaps remain. Regulatory harmonization, tax reform, and the removal of market entry barriers require coordinated policy action beyond the scope of any single pilot project [Van Eijk, 2024, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, Zahler et al., 2025]. Upfront infrastructure costs and the need for standardized, interoperable solutions continue to call for public support and industry-wide collaboration [Micari and Napoli, 2024, Alghawi and Mounsef, 2024, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, Thomas et al., 2023]. To accelerate progress, we recommend regulatory sandboxes for real-world testing, tariff reform to eliminate double charging, and expanded public-private partnerships to share risk and investment [Andersen and Secchi, 2021, Secchi and Andersen, 2023, National Centre for Charging Infrastructure (NOW GmbH), 2024, pv Europe, 2025].

7 Discussion: Smart City and Sustainability Impact

Bidirectional charging is increasingly recognized as a key enabler for the energy transition and smart city development in Europe [Amini et al., 2019, Innovativ, 2024, Zahler et al., 2025]. By integrating EVs as flexible storage assets, cities can enhance grid resilience, reduce CO₂ emissions, and better align energy demand with renewable supply [Zhang et al., 2024, Stogl et al., 2024]. Our Ostra case, while limited in scale and still at an early implementation stage, provides a blueprint for how technical, regulatory, and user barriers can be systematically mapped and addressed. The framework developed here is intentionally designed to be transferable and can be adapted to other cities and regions as regulatory conditions evolve and market incentives mature.

The integration of wireless/5G connectivity further strengthens the business case for bidirectional charging by enabling real-time data exchange, dynamic load management, and seamless interaction with other smart city systems. While the immediate business value of the planned Ostra deployment is modest, the knowledge generated and the frameworks established will inform both local policy in Dresden and broader European strategies for sustainable urban mobility and digital energy transitions.

8 Conclusion and Future Work

This paper presented a Business Model Canvas (BMC)-based framework that combines the planned Ostra pilot design, district-level simulations, and stakeholder mapping for a 5G-enabled bidirectional charging use case in Dresden's Ostra district. Using the BMC as a barrier-detection tool, we systematically linked regulatory, market, user acceptance, and infrastructure barriers to specific V2G (Vehicle-to-Grid) and V2B (Vehicle-to-Building) business model components. It completes our Dresden V2G trilogy: simulation identified Ostra's optimization opportunity, 5G architecture delivered technical feasibility, and this barrier-detection BMC reveals the path to practice. Our findings confirm that while pilots demonstrate technological readiness, large-scale V2G/V2B adoption stalls due to persistent regulatory, market, and user acceptance barriers—the “*faraway water*” gap where future grid benefits fail to address immediate stakeholder needs.

Rather than a commercial business case, we position the Ostra pilot as a systematic “blocker remover” that maps socio-technical barriers across BMC blocks. This framework provides actionable guidance for policymakers (regulatory sandboxes), utilities (V2G tariffs), and city planners (mobility hub integration), aligning incentives for sustainable urban transitions.

Looking forward, the next steps involve refining and disseminating this transferable framework through additional pilots and stakeholder workshops, and using real-world evidence to inform policy development at both local and broader levels. By focusing on systematic barrier removal and knowledge transfer, this work lays the foundation for scalable, resilient, and equitable integration of bidirectional charging in smart city energy systems. From a research perspective, the study illustrates how small-scale pilots can be leveraged not only for technical validation but also for structured socio-technical diagnosis via business model tools. Future work will transfer and refine this barrier-detection BMC in additional European cities and for larger EV fleets, enabling comparative analysis of barrier patterns and the effectiveness of policy interventions such as regulatory sandboxes and new V2G tariffs, as well as empirical validation of the proposed business model under real operational conditions. This will help close the gap between experimental pilots and business-viable, large-scale V2G/V2B deployments.

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